

Acta Medica Young Doctors

Original Article

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Accepted: 2025-09-18

Bibliograph

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.>

Mapping Global Trends and Collaborations in Renal Trauma: A Bibliometric Analysis

ABSTRACT

Background: Renal trauma is the most common form of genitourinary injury and a major concern in emergency medicine, urology, and traumatology. Despite its clinical significance, comprehensive bibliometric evaluations remain scarce. This study aimed to systematically analyze renal trauma literature published between 2005 and 2024, identify influential contributors, visualize collaboration patterns, and highlight research gaps.

Methodology: A bibliometric analysis was conducted using the Web of Science Core Collection. Original research articles in English published between 2005 and 2024 were retrieved with predefined keywords. Bibliometric indicators, including publication counts, citation frequencies, h-index, and citation sum within the h-core (CSh), were calculated. Collaboration networks, keyword co-occurrence, and bibliographic coupling were analyzed using VOSviewer, while BibExcel and

Microsoft Excel were used for data processing.

Results: A total of 464 original articles authored by 2462 researchers from 46 countries and published in 173 journals were analyzed. The United States of America dominated in publication output and citation impact, followed by France, Canada, and China. *The Journal of Urology*, *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*, *Journal of Trauma–Injury, Infection and Critical Care and Urology* were the leading publication venues. Co-occurrence analysis revealed that renal trauma research mainly clusters around the terms kidney, renal trauma, trauma, and wounds and injuries.

Conclusion: This study comprehensively maps renal trauma research, underscoring the need for stronger international collaborations, broader representation of low- and middle-income countries, and innovative approaches to optimize clinical management.

Keywords: Renal trauma, Bibliometric, Research trends, collaboration networks

Introduction

Renal trauma represents the most common form of genitourinary injury and constitutes a significant clinical challenge in the fields of emergency medicine, traumatology, and urology. It most frequently occurs as a result of mechanisms such as motor vehicle collisions, falls from height, and penetrating injuries, often leading to serious complications associated with increased morbidity and mortality.(1, 2) With the growing emphasis on organ-preserving treatment strategies in the management of trauma patients, the accumulation of knowledge in the literature regarding the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of renal injuries has gained even greater importance (3).

Recent advances in imaging techniques, the widespread adoption of minimally invasive interventions, and the implementation of multidisciplinary approaches in trauma centers have led to significant changes in the management of renal trauma (4, 5). Nevertheless, a comprehensive evaluation providing an integrated overview of the distribution of the literature, including the most contributory countries, institutions, authors, and journals, remains lacking. Furthermore, the temporal dynamics of research trends in renal trauma and the evolution of scientific collaborations on a global scale have not been adequately investigated (6).

Bibliometric analysis is a robust method for elucidating both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of scientific output within a specific research domain.⁷ Through this approach, indicators such as publication counts, citation impact, and h-index values can be assessed, while collaboration networks among authors, institutions, and countries are also visualized. Moreover, keyword analyses and bibliographic coupling techniques provide valuable insights into the conceptual development of the field and highlight emerging research trends (8, 9).

This study aims to systematically examine original research articles on renal trauma published between 2005 and 2024 from a bibliometric perspective. To address the gap in the literature, the most productive and influential authors, countries, institutions, and journals

were identified, and collaboration networks, thematic orientations, and temporal trends within the field were analyzed. In this way, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive mapping of the current state of renal trauma research and to generate strategic insights that may guide future investigations.

Materials And Methods

The Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database (<https://www.webofscience.com/>) was used as the data source for the bibliometric analysis. To identify the publications to be included in the study, the “topic” (TS) search field available in the WoS system was selected. In order to comprehensively capture the literature on renal trauma, the following keywords were applied in the search strategy: TS = ((“renal trauma” OR “kidney trauma” OR “renal rupture” OR “kidney rupture” OR “renal laceration” OR “kidney laceration” OR (“genitourinary trauma” AND (kidney OR renal)) OR (“urogenital trauma” AND (kidney OR renal)))). The data retrieval was performed on September 2, 2025.

Publications included in the study consisted of original research articles in English, published between 2005 and 2024 in journals indexed in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-E) within the WoS database. The selected articles were identified through searches conducted using the predefined keywords. Other types of publications that did not qualify as original research articles were excluded from the analysis.

For the processing of bibliometric data, BibExcel software (version 2016-02-20) was used.¹⁰ Microsoft Excel 2016 was employed for data organization, analysis, and visualization.¹¹ During the analysis, the most productive authors, countries, and journals were identified, and for each category, the number of articles, total citation count (cit), h-index (h-i), and citation sum within the h-core (CSh) were calculated. In addition, the top 10 most productive and influential authors were listed for each category.

Network, overlay, and density visualization maps were generated using VOSviewer software (version 1.6.20).¹² The study employed co-authorship, co-occurrence, and bibliographic coupling methods. Multiple approaches were used to evaluate bibliometric relationships. First, co-authorship analysis was performed to demonstrate scientific collaboration networks among researchers. Second, co-occurrence analysis was applied to identify the thematic relationships among concepts used in the literature. Finally, bibliographic coupling was utilized to examine the connections between studies that share similar citation patterns.

The full counting method was used in the analyses, and the association strength approach was applied for link normalization. The layout was optimized with the parameters random start =

1000 and maximum iterations = 1000. These settings improved the consistency of the results by enabling convergence not only to local minima but also to a more general optimum. In the network maps, items were visualized as nodes and their relationships as links. Furthermore, the total link strength (TLS) value calculated for each item was used to indicate the degree of interaction and the intensity of relationships within the network.

In the co-authorship analysis, inter-institutional collaboration was evaluated. Cluster density visualization was applied for this analysis. Each item represented an institution and was color-coded according to its cluster, with the colors reflecting the relational proximity among the items. The weight of a given cluster color (light to dark) was determined by the number of items located near a given point within that cluster. For the construction of the cluster density map, the filtering thresholds were set as a minimum of five documents per author and a minimum of 30 citations per author. The weighting of items was based on the number of documents. Increased brightness (density) of the items indicated a higher number of documents associated with that institution. To distinguish small-scale clusters and enhance visualization sensitivity, the kernel width parameter for density was set to the minimum level.

The relationships among keywords were examined using co-occurrence analysis. This method was applied to author-defined keywords appearing in the same publication in order to reveal the conceptual structure of the research field. In the visualizations generated with the network visualization technique, the most frequently used keywords were displayed together with the terms they most commonly co-occurred with. Each keyword was represented as a node in the map, and the links between nodes reflected the frequency of their co-occurrence within the same publication. The size of each node indicated the frequency of use of that term in the literature. A minimum threshold of five was set for the inclusion of keywords in the analysis. The weighting of the nodes was based on their frequency of co-occurrence. To demonstrate the conceptual and temporal trends within the field, overlay visualization was performed for the two most frequently used keywords. In this analysis, nodes represented the respective items, while the color scale reflected their time of emergence and frequency of use. Thus, the developmental dynamics of the field were visualized. In overlay visualization, the color scale of the nodes was determined using the average publication year (APY) values.

Bibliographic coupling analysis was employed to examine the similarity among articles. This method reveals the relationships between studies based on the references they share. By applying a minimum citation threshold of 10, the clustering of prominent studies and the

visualization of thematic structures were achieved. The weighting of nodes was based on citation counts.

Results

Using the predefined search strategy in the Web of Science database, a total of 1704 publications related to renal trauma were identified. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 464 original research articles were included in the analysis. These articles were authored by 2462 researchers from 46 different countries and were published across 173 distinct journals. The study process is illustrated in a flow diagram presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flow diagram demonstrating the screening and inclusion process of the studies

The top 10 most productive and influential authors in the field of renal trauma are presented in Table 1. The three most productive authors, who also had the highest h-index values, were Benjamin N. Breyer (25 articles, h-index = 14), Jeremy B. Myers (22 articles, h-index = 12), and Sorena M. Keihani (16 articles, h-index = 12). In terms of citation sum within the h-core (CSh), the leading three authors were Hunter Wessells (7 articles, CSh = 401), Benjamin N. Breyer (25 articles, CSh = 400), and James M. Hotaling (12 articles, CSh = 400).

The United States of America (USA) had the highest number of publications, h-index, and CSh values (200 articles, CSh = 2362, h-index = 33). Following the USA, the countries with the highest h-index and CSh values were France (23 articles, h-index = 11) and Canada (13 articles, h-index = 10). In terms of publication count, after the USA, the leading countries were the People's Republic of China (34 articles, h-index = 8) and France (23 articles, h-index = 11).

The journals with the highest h-index and CSh values were the Journal of Urology (39 articles, CSh = 1087, h-index = 22), the Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery (29 articles, CSh = 802, h-index = 14), and the Journal of Trauma–Injury, Infection and Critical Care (15 articles, CSh = 657, h-index = 12). In terms of publication count, following the Journal of Urology (39 articles), the leading journals were the Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery (29 articles) and Urology (29 articles).

As illustrated in Figure 2, the countries with the highest number of publications are presented.

Figure 2. Treemap visualization of the countries contributing the highest number of publications on renal trauma (the values shown next to each country correspond to the total article count)

Figure 3. Cluster density visualization map of organizations co-authorships

Figure 6. Bibliographic coupling analysis showing the network of document relationships

To illustrate inter-institutional collaboration, a cluster density map was generated and is presented in Figure 3. Among 812 institutions, a co-authorship analysis was conducted for those with a minimum of five publications and at least 30 citations (a total of 29 institutions), with documents selected as the weighting unit. The analysis yielded four clusters, 210 links, and a total link strength (TLS) of 1065. In this visualization, the institutions with the highest number of publications were the University of Washington (36 articles), the University of California, San Francisco (26 articles), and the University of Utah (22 articles). The institutions with the highest citation counts were the University of Washington (725 citations), the University of California, San Francisco (530 citations), and the University of Maryland (459 citations). The institutions with the highest TLS values were the University of Utah (TLS = 155), the University of California, San Francisco (TLS = 136), and Loma Linda University (TLS = 129).

In Figure 4, the frequency of co-occurrence and interrelationships of keywords within the same publications were demonstrated using co-occurrence analysis. A minimum threshold of five publications per keyword was applied. Among 825 keywords, 58 met this criterion, and after excluding one disconnected keyword, 57 were included in the analysis. The results identified 10 clusters, 351 links, and a total link strength (TLS) of 786. Weighting was based on co-occurrence frequency. The most frequently co-occurring keywords were kidney (86 occurrences, TLS = 186), renal trauma (83 occurrences, TLS = 127), trauma (66 occurrences, TLS = 132), wounds and injuries (37 occurrences, TLS = 93), and nephrectomy (37 occurrences, TLS = 89). These five terms also represented the keywords with the highest TLS values. The strongest keyword pairs were “kidney–trauma” (27 links), “kidney–wounds and injuries” (26 links), “trauma–renal trauma” (16 links), “kidney–nephrectomy” (13 links), and “renal trauma–nephrectomy” (10 links).

In Figure 5, an overlay visualization was generated within the co-occurrence analysis using the average publication year (APY) as the criterion. This visualization allowed the temporal connections of the two most frequently used keywords, kidney and renal trauma, with other terms to be assessed. The APY was calculated as 2012.90 for the keyword kidney and 2016.72 for renal trauma. The results indicated that the keyword renal trauma was associated with relatively more recently used terms compared with kidney.

In Figure 6, a network map was generated using bibliographic coupling analysis to demonstrate the relationships among documents with similar citation histories. Only documents that had received at least 30 citations were included in the analysis. Among the 464 documents, 67 met this threshold, of which 64 were found to be interconnected. Citation counts were used as the weighting measure. The analysis identified 8 clusters, 956 links, and a total link strength (TLS) of 118. The most highly cited studies were those by Kozar (2018) (326 citations, TLS = 58), Kuan (2006) (112 citations, TLS = 82), Harrois (2018) (106 citations, TLS = 4), Breyer (2008) (104 citations, TLS = 69), and Snedeker (2005b) (100 citations, TLS = 6). The documents with the highest total link strength were McCombie (2014) (41 citations, TLS = 192), Bukur (2011) (32 citations, TLS = 167), Buckley (2006) (42 citations, TLS = 151), Fitzgerald (2011) (33 citations, TLS = 149), and Charbit (2011) (51 citations, TLS = 135).

Discussion

This study represents one of the most up-to-date investigations to comprehensively examine the renal trauma literature using bibliometric methods. The findings revealed that between 2005 and 2024, a total of 464 original research articles on renal trauma were published, with the majority originating from developed countries such as the United States of America, France, and Canada. The clear dominance of the United States of America in both publication output and citation performance may be attributed to its high-volume trauma centers, the routine use of advanced imaging modalities, the widespread application of minimally invasive interventions, and the effective integration of multidisciplinary treatment strategies (13-15). At the same time, this highlights the unequal distribution within the global literature.

Author and institutional analyses clearly demonstrate the influence of leading research groups and established academic centers in the field of renal trauma. The prominence of authors such as Breyer, Myers, and Keihani indicates that highly cited studies are concentrated within specific centers, which generate guideline-shaping data with direct implications for clinical practice. Similarly, bibliometric studies in kidney disease and therapeutic approaches have shown that global research output is largely clustered around a few high-volume academic institutions and leading investigators, with scientific directions being strongly shaped by these centers (16). Among institutions, the University of Washington and the University of California, San Francisco emerged as prominent

contributors, underscoring the pivotal role of U.S.-based academic structures in leading the global research network in this field. This is particularly evident in the Multi-institutional Genito-Urinary Trauma Study (MiGUTS), where the active participation of UCSF and UW was central to advancing knowledge on the management of Grade V renal trauma (17). However, the relatively limited contributions from low- and middle-income countries highlight a disparity in global representation. This imbalance restricts the inclusion of diverse patient profiles, trauma mechanisms, and treatment strategies from different regions, thereby limiting the comprehensiveness of the literature.

An analysis of journal distribution revealed that the *The Journal of Urology*, *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*, *Journal of Trauma–Injury, Infection and Critical Care* and *Urology* ranked among the leading platforms in terms of publication performance. This finding demonstrates that renal trauma research is strongly represented in both the urological and traumatological literature, while also being disseminated across different publication platforms consistent with its interdisciplinary nature. However, the relatively limited number of studies focusing on pediatric trauma, radiological diagnostic approaches, and minimally invasive interventions indicates a gap in the literature in these specific areas (18, 19).

Keyword analysis revealed that the most frequently used terms were kidney, renal trauma, trauma, and nephrectomy, indicating that the literature has long been concentrated on surgical

and organ-loss-oriented approaches. In overlay analysis, the association of the keyword renal trauma with more recently emerging terms suggests that research trends in recent years have increasingly focused on conservative management, organ-preserving surgery, endovascular interventions, and long-term post-trauma outcomes (20, 21). The results of bibliographic coupling demonstrated that, despite thematic diversity, research remained clustered around specific subfields, suggesting that innovative perspectives are still limited. Indeed, the analysis showed that studies were predominantly grouped around surgical interventions, conservative treatment strategies, imaging techniques, and endovascular procedures, whereas innovative contributions in areas such as long-term functional outcomes, pediatric trauma, and artificial intelligence-assisted diagnostic strategies remain relatively scarce (13).

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the development of the renal trauma literature, demonstrating that research output has been concentrated around specific countries, institutions, and authors, while highlighting the need for a more balanced global distribution. The findings reveal that international collaborations remain limited and that multicenter studies are insufficient. In the future, it will be crucial to generate more data from low- and middle-income countries, to strengthen multicenter and interdisciplinary collaborations, and to evaluate new imaging techniques and minimally invasive approaches in larger patient

populations. Moreover, increasing the number of studies addressing long-term renal functional outcomes and quality of life after trauma may help reduce disparities in the literature. Ultimately, these efforts would allow renal trauma management to be grounded in a more balanced, globally representative, and evidence-based foundation, both clinically and academically.

No	Authors	All articles	Citation sum within h-core	All citations	h-index
1	Breyer, Benjamin N	25	400	459	14
2	Myers, Jeremy B	22	254	295	12
3	Keihani, Sorena M	16	192	199	12
4	Hotaling, James M	12	400	400	12
5	Voelzke, Bryan B	12	310	314	11
6	Santucci, Richard A	11	255	258	10
7	McAninch, Jack W	9	373	378	9
8	Hagedorn, Judith C	17	88	108	8
9	Baradaran, Nima	14	176	195	8
10	Nirula, Raminder	13	173	193	8
No	Countries	All articles	Citation sum within h-core	All citations	h-index
1	USA	200	2362	4230	33
2	France	23	455	504	11
3	Canada	13	339	357	10
4	Peoples R China	34	153	235	8
5	Japan	18	120	137	8
6	The United Kingdom	18	187	233	7
7	Türkiye	19	67	109	6
8	Germany	11	127	142	6
9	Italy	10	187	194	6
10	Iran	7	90	90	6
No	Journal Names	All articles	Citation sum within h-core	All citations	h-index
1	Journal of Urology	39	1087	1259	22
2	Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery	29	802	930	14
3	Journal of Trauma-Injury Infection and Critical Care	15	657	685	12
4	Urology	29	174	241	10
5	Journal of Pediatric Urology	13	90	97	7
6	BJU International	9	236	249	7
7	World Journal of Urology	16	100	120	6
8	Injury-International Journal of The Care of The Injured	10	98	108	6
9	Radiographics	6	252	252	6
10	Journal of Pediatric Surgery	6	131	131	6

Table 1. The top 10 authors, countries, and journals that have made the most significant contributions to renal trauma research

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